

Vulnerability Analysis against Stealthy Integrity Attacks for Nonlinear Systems

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Abstract—This paper considers the vulnerability issues of a class of nonlinear systems to stealthy integrity attacks. To characterize the stealthiness of the attack, a forward-invariant set for the system output is introduced. Additionally, a safety set for the system state is established to evaluate the attack’s safety. Our analysis demonstrates that the nonlinear system is non-vulnerable to strictly stealthy integrity attacks if it is uniformly observable. When the uniform observability property is not satisfied, we show that the considered class of nonlinear systems is not vulnerable to stealthy integrity attacks when an output-to-state safe barrier function is admitted. Moreover, for nonlinear systems that are vulnerable to stealthy integrity attacks, we analytically show how these are parameterized. Our analytic results are validated with numerical simulations that demonstrate the applicability of the presented analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

A wide range of safety-critical systems, such as power grids, transportation networks, and water distribution networks, are characterized as nonlinear Cyber-physical systems (CPS). The control, computation, and communication techniques integrated into CPS make them vulnerable to malicious cyber attacks [1], [2]. Significant research focus is paid to risk management, of which an important aspect is the attack vulnerability analysis [2]. Assessing whether nonlinear systems are vulnerable to stealthy integrity attacks is a subject of critical importance for addressing latent security weaknesses and preventing malicious incidents.

Considering stealthy integrity attacks, the vulnerability of linear systems has been recently studied in [3]–[5], by considering the stability of the zero dynamics of the underlying linear system. The vulnerability of a system is determined by the input-to-state stability of its internal dynamics. For linear systems, this is the same as the stability of the zero dynamics, which is well-proved in [6]. However, as demonstrated in [7], for nonlinear systems, the stability of the zero dynamics differs from the input-to-state stability

This work has been supported by: the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 101027980 (CSP-CPS-A-ICA), the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 739551 (KIOS CoE), the Republic of Cyprus through the Directorate General for European Programs, Coordination, and Development, and by the Swedish Foundation for Strategic Research.

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of the internal dynamics, which motivates this work. The vulnerability of nonlinear systems to a special class of sensor false-data injection attacks based on the incremental stability of the open-loop and closed-loop systems is studied in [8]. To the best of the authors’ knowledge, the existing literature lacks an explicit characterization of the system properties that render nonlinear systems non-vulnerable to stealthy integrity attacks. Furthermore, no previous vulnerability analysis has leveraged forward invariance concepts to formally define attack stealthiness or utilized safety sets to rigorously evaluate the safety implications of such attacks.

Contribution: This paper considers the vulnerability issues to stealthy integrity attacks for a class of nonlinear systems. We first establish the framework for analyzing the vulnerability of nonlinear systems to stealthy integrity attacks by providing suitable definitions of strictly/non-strictly stealthy inputs, safe inputs, and stealthy integrity attacks that facilitate our analysis. Moreover, we introduce a forward invariant set for the system output to characterize the attack stealthiness and a safety set for the system states to assess the system’s safety against attacks. Our analysis demonstrates that nonlinear systems are non-vulnerable to strictly stealthy integrity attack if they are uniformly observable. Moreover, for nonlinear systems that are not uniformly observable, we show that if the nonlinear system admits an output-to-state safe barrier function, then it is not vulnerable to stealthy integrity attacks. Furthermore, for nonlinear systems that are vulnerable to stealthy integrity attacks, we analytically show how these are parameterized. The applicability of the presented theoretical results is validated through suitable examples and numerical simulations.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

A. System Description

An affine closed-loop nonlinear CPS subject to actuator integrity type of cyber attacks is considered as follows:

$$\dot{x} = f(x) + g(x)a(t), \quad x(t_0) = x_0, \quad (1a)$$

$$y = h(x), \quad (1b)$$

where $x \in \mathcal{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ (in the global case $\mathcal{X} = \mathbb{R}^n$) and $y \in \mathbb{R}^m$ are the state and output respectively, and $a \in \mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^m$ with \mathcal{A} being the admissible attack set, represents the actuator attack signal and is assumed to be smooth. The attack occurs at time t_0 , and x_0 is the initial state at t_0 . It should be noted that within this paper, the terms inputs and attacks are used interchangeably in contexts where the distinction is clear, since the input to (1) is the attack signal. The functions

$f : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$, $g : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ and $h : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ are assumed to be smooth. Note that f represents the closed-loop vector field, including the physical plant and the controller. This closed-loop system in the nominal scenario, i.e., when there is no attack, is given as follows:

$$\dot{x}_n = f(x_n), \quad x_n(t_0) = x_0, \quad (2a)$$

$$y_n = h(x_n) \quad (2b)$$

where x_n and y_n are the nominal state and output respectively.

B. Stealthy Attack and Safety Region

Stealthiness and destructiveness are two key characteristics of stealthy integrity attacks. They are described in detail below through the definitions of stealthy integrity attacks and the safety region. To this end, the deviation between $y(t, t_0, x_0, a)$ and $y_n(t, t_0, x_0, 0)$, where $y(t, t_0, x_0, a)$ and $y_n(t, t_0, x_0, 0)$ represent the output trajectories of system (1) and (2) respectively, is denoted by

$$\Delta y(t, t_0, x_0, a) \triangleq y(t, t_0, x_0, a) - y_n(t, t_0, x_0, 0).$$

It should be noted that $\Delta y(t) \equiv 0$ for $t \geq 0$ can be achieved by both static and dynamic inputs. Based on [7], [9], and the well-established fully actuated control method in [10], a dynamic input can be equivalently replaced by a static input utilizing the high-order derivative of the output Δy . Hence, this work considers attacks of the following static feedback form:

$$a(t) \triangleq a_1(x(t), x_n(t)) + a_2(x(t), x_n(t))v(t), \quad \forall t \geq t_0, \quad (3)$$

where a_1 and a_2 are suitable smooth, vector-valued, memoryless functions, and $v(t)$ is a continuous time-varying signal satisfying $v(t) \neq 0$ for $t \geq t_0$. Under $a(t)$, both systems (1) and (2) are forward complete, i.e., the solutions to (1) and (2) exist and are unique for all $t \geq t_0$ and all $a \in \mathcal{A}$.

The following sets are defined to enable the characterization of stealthy and safe inputs. To characterize inputs as stealthy, we first define the stealthy output set $\Delta \mathcal{Y}$ such that no anomaly detector is triggered if $\Delta y \in \Delta \mathcal{Y}$. Without loss of generality, $\Delta \mathcal{Y}$ is defined as follows

$$\Delta \mathcal{Y} = \mathcal{R}(s_y, \mathcal{D}_y) \triangleq \{\Delta y \in \mathcal{D}_y : s_y(y - y_n) \geq 0\}, \quad (4)$$

where $s_y : \mathbb{R}^{n_y} \rightarrow \mathcal{R}$ is a continuously differentiable function such that $\Delta \mathcal{Y}$ is a closed set, and \mathcal{D}_y is an open set such that $\mathcal{D}_y \supseteq \Delta \mathcal{Y}$. Next, we formally define the concepts of strictly stealthy and non-strictly stealthy inputs.

Definition 1 (Strictly/Non-strictly Stealthy Input). An input $a(t) \in \mathcal{A}$, as in (3), is called strictly stealthy if $\Delta y(t, t_0, x_0, a) \equiv 0$ for all $t \geq t_0$ and non-strictly stealthy if $\Delta y(t, t_0, x_0, a) \in \Delta \mathcal{Y}$ for all $t \geq t_0$. ■

Both the strictly and non-strictly stealthy attacks are referred to as stealthy attacks in this paper. Regarding the safety of an attack, [3] and [11] assess the safety of an input by whether this input drives the system state to infinity. In practice, steering the system state out of a safety region, rather than driving it to infinity, is sufficient to harm a system,

which motivates providing a definition of a safety region. Inspired by [12], [13], the safety region, denoted by \mathcal{S} , is defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{S} \triangleq \mathcal{R}(s, \mathcal{D}_s) \triangleq \{x \in \mathcal{D}_s : s(x) \geq 0\}, \quad (5)$$

where $s : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, is a continuously differentiable function and \mathcal{D}_s is an open set such that $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{D}_s$. Based on [13], the autonomous system (2) is safe with respect to \mathcal{S} if \mathcal{S} is forward invariant with respect to (2). In addition, for the non-autonomous system (1) driven by an attack $a(t)$, we introduce the input-to-state safe (ISSf) set [14]. The set \mathcal{S} is ISSf if $\mathcal{S}_a \supseteq \mathcal{S}$ is forward invariant, where

$$\mathcal{S}_a \triangleq \{x \in \mathcal{D}_s : s(x) + \gamma(\|a\|_\infty) \geq 0\}, \quad (6)$$

for some class $\mathcal{K}_{[0, \bar{d}]}$ function γ and $\|a\|_\infty < \bar{d}$. A system is ISSf if it admits an ISSf set. Then, we define a safe input as follows.

Definition 2 (Safe Input). Consider (3) and suppose that $v(t)$ is bounded, i.e., $\|v(t)\|_\infty \leq \bar{d}$ for $t \geq t_0$. Then, $a(t)$ is a safe input with respect to \mathcal{S} if \mathcal{S} is ISSf with respect to \mathcal{S}_a . ■

Using the definitions of stealthy attack and safe input in Definitions 1 and 2 respectively, we can define the stealthy integrity attack as follows.

Definition 3 (Stealthy Integrity Attack). An input $a(t) \in \mathcal{A}$ in (3), is a (strictly) stealthy integrity attack if it is a (strictly) stealthy input but not a safe input. ■

A system is vulnerable to stealthy integrity attacks if there exist stealthy inputs that are not safe. Otherwise, a system is safe. Hence, to analyze the system's vulnerability to stealthy integrity attacks, two fundamental aspects are required to be rigorously explored: (a) the existence of stealthy attacks and (b) whether stealthy attacks are safe. To focus on investigating the attack vulnerability of system (1) with safety region \mathcal{S} , we assume that the attacker has exact knowledge of f , g , h , and the safe region \mathcal{S} , and also knowledge of x_n and x .

C. Problem Statement

Below, we present the problem considered in this paper.

Problem 1. For the nonlinear system (1) with the attack $a(t)$, given by (3), obtain conditions under which the system is not vulnerable to stealthy integrity attacks. In particular, define conditions such that no stealthy attack exists.

Solving Problem 1 guarantees that a system is not vulnerable to stealthy integrity attacks, allowing its operator to exclude this possibility.

III. STEALTHY INPUTS

To facilitate the presentation of this work, we rewrite systems (1), (2), and the expression for Δy in the following

compact form:

$$\dot{x} = f(x) + g(x)a(t), \quad x(t_0) = x_0, \quad (7a)$$

$$\dot{x}_n = f(x_n), \quad x_n(t_0) = x_0, \quad (7b)$$

$$\Delta y = y - y_n. \quad (7c)$$

Below, we present necessary and sufficient conditions for the existence of a stealthy input. To enable this, we introduce the concept of a uniformly observable. To this end, we use $x(t, t_0, x_0, a)$, $x_n(t, t_0, x_0, a)$ and $y(t, t_0, x_0, a)$, $y_n(t, t_0, x_0, a)$ and $\Delta y_n(t, t_0, x_0, a)$ to represent the trajectories of the states and outputs of systems (1), (2), and (7), with initial condition x_0 and input a for $t \geq t_0$.

Definition 4 (Uniformly Observable). [15] Consider an open set \mathcal{X} such that $x \in \mathcal{X}$. System (1) is uniformly observable on \mathcal{X} if when $x_1 \neq x_2$, then for any input a , all $x_1, x_2 \in \mathcal{X}$, and all $t \geq t_0$, $y(t, t_0, x_1, a) \neq y(t, t_0, x_2, a)$. ■

Based on the concept of a uniformly observable system, we derive the following result.

Theorem 1. *Suppose that in the presence of $a(t) \neq 0$ in (3), the state of system (7a) satisfies $x(t, t_0, x_0, a) \neq x(t, t_0, x_0, 0)$ for $t > t_0$. Then, the system (1) does not admit any strictly stealthy input if and only if it is uniformly observable for any input $a(t)$.* ■

Theorem 1 shows that when the system is uniformly observable, it is not vulnerable to strictly stealthy attack. Condition $x(t, t_0, x_0, a) \neq x(t, t_0, x_0, 0)$ for $a(t) \neq 0$ is a very practical consideration in the context of the malicious attack. The attacker must choose the attack signal that affects the system efficiently, which requires the condition. Next, we explore the case where system (1) is not uniformly observable. More specifically, we investigate the static stealthy input $a(t) \in \mathcal{A}$ in (3) by using the high-order derivatives of y and y_n . Based on [16], the steps are shown as follows:

Step 1: We have

$$\dot{y} = \tilde{h}_1(x) + \tilde{J}_1(x)a, \quad (8)$$

where $\tilde{h}_1(x) = \frac{\partial h(x)}{\partial x} f(x)$, $\tilde{J}_1(x) = \frac{\partial h(x)}{\partial x} g(x)$. Without loss of generality, we let $\text{rank}(\tilde{J}_1(x)) = r_1$ for any $x \in \mathcal{X}$ and the first r_1 rows be linearly independent for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$. Then, by partitioning all the vectors in (8), we obtain that

$$\dot{y}_{1 \dots r_1} = h_1(x) + J_1(x)a, \quad (9)$$

and

$$\dot{y}_{r_1+1 \dots p} = \hat{h}_1(x) + \hat{J}_1(x)a, \quad (10)$$

where h_1 and \hat{h}_1 are the first r_1 rows and the last $p-r_1$ rows of \tilde{h}_1 , respectively. In addition, $J_1(x)$ is of full row rank, and there exists some matrix $F_1(x) \in \mathbb{R}^{p-r_1 \times r_1}$ such that $\hat{J}_1 = F_1(x)J_1(x)$. From (9), we have $J_1(x)a = \dot{y}_{1 \dots r_1} - h_1(x)$. By substituting this into (10), we obtain

$$\dot{y}_{r_1+1 \dots p} = \bar{h}_1(x, \dot{y}_{1 \dots r_1}) \triangleq \hat{h}_1(x) + F_1(x) (\dot{y}_{1 \dots r_1} - h_1(x)). \quad (11)$$

Step k: By differentiating the following equations obtained at step $k-1$

$$y_{r_{k-1}+1 \dots p}^{(k-1)} = \bar{h}_{k-1}(x, \dot{y}_{1 \dots r_1}, \ddot{y}_{1 \dots r_2}, \dots, y_{1 \dots r_{k-1}}^{(k-1)}), \quad (12)$$

we obtain that

$$y_{r_{k-1}+1 \dots p}^{(k)} = \tilde{h}_{k-1}(x, \dot{y}_{1 \dots r_1}, \dots, y_{1 \dots r_{k-1}}^{(k)}) + \tilde{J}_{k-1}(x, \dot{y}_{1 \dots r_1}, \dots, y_{1 \dots r_{k-1}}^{(k-1)})a, \quad (13)$$

where $\tilde{h}_{k-1}(\cdot) = \frac{\partial \bar{h}_{k-1}}{\partial x} f(x) + \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \sum_{i=1}^{r_j} \frac{\partial \bar{h}_{k-1}}{\partial y_i^{(j)}} y_i^{(j+1)}$ and $\tilde{J}_{k-1}(x, \dot{y}_{1 \dots r_1}, \dots, y_{1 \dots r_{k-1}}^{(k-1)}) = \frac{\partial \bar{h}_{k-1}}{\partial x} g(x)$. At this general step, we make the following assumptions.

Assumption 1. The $m \times m$ matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} J_1(x) \\ J_2(x, \dot{y}_{1 \dots r_1}) \\ \dots \\ \tilde{J}_k(x, \dot{y}_{1 \dots r_1}, \dots, y_{1 \dots r_{k-1}}^{(k-1)}) \end{pmatrix} \quad (14)$$

has a constant rank r_k for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$ and the first $r_k - r_{k-1}$ rows of \tilde{J}_k are linearly independent of J_1, \dots, J_{k-1} for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$ and $\dot{y}_{1 \dots r_1}, \dots, y_{1 \dots r_{k-1}}^{(k-1)}$. ▼

Assumption 2. There exists some constant $k^* \leq n$ such that the rank of $\tilde{J}_{k^*}(x)$, denoted by r_{k^*} , satisfies $r_{k^*} = m$ for any $x \in \mathcal{X}$. ▼

Suppose that the outputs are reordered such that Assumption 1 is satisfied. From Assumption 2, since $r_{k^*} = m$, by taking different order derivatives of the outputs based on the aforementioned steps, the following holds:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{y}_{1 \dots r_1} \\ y_{r_1+1 \dots r_2}^{(2)} \\ \dots \\ y_{r_{k^*}-1+1, \dots, r_{k^*}}^{(k^*)} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} h_1(x) \\ h_2(x, \dot{y}_{1 \dots r_1}, \ddot{y}_{1 \dots r_1}) \\ \dots \\ h_{k^*}(x, \dot{y}_{1 \dots r_1}, \dots, y_{1 \dots r_{k^*}-1}^{(k^*)}) \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} J_1(x) \\ J_2(x, \dot{y}_{1 \dots r_1}) \\ \dots \\ J_{k^*}(x, \dot{y}_{1 \dots r_1}, \dots, y_{1 \dots r_{k^*}-1}^{(k^*-1)}) \end{bmatrix} a(t). \quad (15)$$

Given some \mathbb{R}^l -valued vector y and a nonnegative integer k , we define the following $\mathbb{R}^{k(l+1)}$ -valued vector

$$y^k(y) \triangleq (y_1; \dots; y_1^{(k)}; \dots; y_l; \dots; y_l^{(k)}). \quad (16)$$

Then, an m -valued vector is induced as follows:

$$y_m \triangleq (y^0(y_{1, \dots, r_1}); \dots; y^{k^*-1}(y_{r_{k^*}-1+1, \dots, m})). \quad (17)$$

Based on (16) and (17), (15) can be written as

$$\frac{dy_m}{dt} = H(x, y^{(k^*)}(y_{1, \dots, r_{k^*}-1})) + J(x, y^{(k^*-1)}(y_{1, \dots, r_{k^*}-1}))a(t), \quad (18)$$

where $H = [h_1^T, h_2^T, \dots, h_{k^*}^T]^T$ and $J = [J_1^T, J_2^T, \dots, J_{k^*}^T]^T$. Let $z_{l,i}$ denote the i -th element

of y_{r_{l-1}, \dots, r_l} with $i \in \{r_{l-1}, \dots, r_l\}$. Then, it follows from (15) that

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{z}_{l,i,1} &= z_{l,i,2}, \quad \dot{z}_{l,i,2} = z_{l,i,3}, \\ &\vdots \\ \dot{z}_{l,i,l} &= h_{l,i}(x, y^{(l)}(y_{1, \dots, r_{l-1}})) \\ &\quad + J_{l,i}(x, y^{(l-1)}(y_{1, \dots, r_{l-1}}))a(t), \\ y_i &= z_{l,i,1}, \quad \forall i \in \{r_{l-1}, \dots, r_l\}. \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Note that such a system is uniformly observable with respect to $a(t)$. It should be also noted that since the nominal system (2) and the attacked system (1) have the same flow and output vector fields, by taking the same operations from *step 1* to *step k*, the nominal system can also be transformed into the form of (15). Let $z = (z_1; \dots; z_l; \dots; z_{k^*})$ where $z_l = (z_{l,1}; \dots; z_{l,r_l-r_{l-1}})$ for $l \in \{1, \dots, k^*\}$. Correspondingly, we can define z_n and $z_{n,l}$ in the nominal case.

Then, an input $a(t)$ is parameterized as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} a(t) &= -J(\cdot)^{-1} \left(H(x, y^{(k^*)}(y_{1, \dots, r_{k^*-1}})) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - H(x, y^{(k^*)}(y_{n1, \dots, r_{k^*-1}})) - G(z - z_n) + v(t) \right), \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where $v(t)$ is some continuous time-varying and bounded signal to be specified later. Let $G_l \in \mathbb{R}^{(r_l-r_{l-1}) \times l(r_l-r_{l-1})}$ for $l = 1, \dots, k^*$ where $G_{l,i}$ is such that the polynomial using $G_{l,i}$ as its coefficient vector is stable. Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned} G &\in \mathcal{G} \\ &\triangleq \{\text{diag}(G_1, \dots, G_{k^*}), G_l \in \mathbb{R}^{(r_l-r_{l-1}) \times l(r_l-r_{l-1})}\}. \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

The definition of control barrier function, utilized to state Theorem 2, is presented below.

Definition 5. [14] Given a closed set $\mathcal{S} \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ defined by (5) for a continuously differentiable function $s : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, the function s is called a control barrier function (CBF) defined on the open set \mathcal{D}_s with $\mathcal{S} \subset \mathcal{D}_s$ for system (1) if there exists a set \mathcal{A} , and an extended class \mathcal{K} function α such that

$$\sup_{a \in \mathcal{A}} L_{f+ga}s(x) \geq -\alpha(s(x)), \quad (22)$$

holds for all $x \in \mathcal{D}_s$. ■

Below, we present the following main result.

Theorem 2. *Suppose Assumptions 1 and 2 hold. Consider the attack $a(t)$ in (20) with $G \in \mathcal{G}$ in (21). Then, $a(t)$ is strictly stealthy if and only if $v(t) \equiv 0$. Moreover, for the stealthy output set $\Delta\mathcal{Y}$, given by (4), with the continuously differentiable function s_y , $a(t)$ is a stealthy attack if $v(t) \in \mathcal{V}$ is chosen such that $\Delta\mathcal{Y}$ admits a control barrier function on the set \mathcal{D}_y with $\Delta\mathcal{Y} \subset \mathcal{D}_y$, i.e.,*

$$\mathcal{V} \triangleq \{L_{A(G)+Ev}s_y(\Delta y) \geq -\alpha(s_y(\Delta y)), \forall \Delta y \in \mathcal{D}_y\}, \quad (23)$$

where α is some extended class \mathcal{K} function. ■

Proof: By letting $\Delta z_l \triangleq z_l - z_{n,l}$ denote the deviation between z_l and $z_{n,l}$, it follows from (19) that under the parameterized attack (20),

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \dot{z}_{l,i,1} &= \Delta z_{l,i,2}, \quad \Delta \dot{z}_{l,i,2} = \Delta z_{l,i,3}, \\ &\dots \\ \Delta \dot{z}_{l,i,l} &= G_{l,i} \Delta z_{l,i} + v_{r_{l+i}}(t), \\ \Delta y_i &= \Delta z_{l,i,1}, \quad \forall i \in \{r_{l-1}, \dots, r_l\}. \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

Note that due to the design of $G_{l,i}$ in (21), system (24) is stable. Then, by letting $\Delta z = z - z_n$ denote the deviation between z and z_n , based on (24), we deduce that

$$\Delta \dot{z} = A(G)\Delta z + Ev, \quad (25a)$$

$$\Delta y = C\Delta z, \quad (25b)$$

where $A(G)$, E and C are obtained based on (15), (20) and (24). This system is uniformly observable for any $v(t)$ and is controllable.

Note that system (25) is uniformly observable and controllable. Hence, to guarantee $\Delta y(t) \equiv 0$ for $t \geq t_0$ such that the attack is strictly stealthy, $v(t)$ must be zero identically. In addition, based on Definition 5, if (23) holds, then $\Delta\mathcal{Y}$ is forward invariant, and hence, $\Delta y(t) \in \Delta\mathcal{Y}$ for all $t \geq t_0$. Hence, the attack is non-strictly stealthy. □

Based on Theorem 2, the strictly stealthy input set and the non-strictly stealthy input set, of which every element having the form (20), denoted as \mathcal{A}_0 and \mathcal{A}_1 , respectively, can be determined by the matrix $G \in \mathcal{G}$ in (21) and $v(t) \in \mathcal{V}$ in (23).

IV. SAFETY OF STEALTHY INPUTS

Under the input $a(t)$ in (20), there exists a diffeomorphism coordinate transformation $\phi : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ such that in the new coordinates $(\eta; z) = \phi(x)$ and $(\eta_n; z_n) = \phi(x_n)$. Then, system (7) can be written as

$$\dot{\eta} = q(\eta, z), \quad \eta(t_0) = \eta_0, \quad (26a)$$

$$\dot{\eta}_n = q(\eta_n, z_n), \quad \eta_n(t_0) = \eta_{n0}, \quad (26b)$$

$$\dot{z} = A(G)z + Ev, \quad z(t_0) = z_0, \quad (26c)$$

$$\dot{z}_n = A(G)z_n, \quad z_n(t_0) = z_{n0}, \quad (26d)$$

$$\Delta y = C(z - z_n), \quad (26e)$$

where $\eta, \eta_n \in \mathbb{R}^{n - \sum_{l=1}^{k^*} l(r_l - r_{l-1})}$.

In the presence of a strictly stealthy input $a(t) \in \mathcal{A}_0$, $\Delta z = z - z_n = 0$, and thus, $\eta = \eta_n$, which is trivial and is a safe input for any internal dynamics (26a). Hence, in the following, we consider the non-strictly stealthy input $a(t) \in \mathcal{A}_1$. Since the pair $(A(G), C)$ is observable, for $\Delta y \in \Delta\mathcal{Y}$, the region of Δz , that is determined by $v(t) \in \mathcal{V}$, can be easily derived. We let $\Delta\mathcal{Z}$ be the forward invariant set of Δz , i.e.,

$$\Delta z(t, t_0, v) \in \Delta\mathcal{Z} = \{z : \|z\| \leq N\}, \quad \forall v(t) \in \mathcal{V}, \quad (27)$$

where $N \in \mathbb{R}_+$ represents the bound, and $\Delta z(t, t_0, v)$ is the trajectory of the system (25) with the input $v(t)$.

Consider a system (1) with an output $y_a = y + \Delta y(t)$ subject to perturbation $\Delta y(t)$ where $\|\Delta y\|_\infty < \bar{d}$ for any

$t \geq t_0$. In analogy with the ISSf set \mathcal{S}_a with respect to input a in (6), we define a safe region \mathcal{S}_y with respect to output perturbation Δy as follows:

$$\mathcal{S}_y \triangleq \{x \in \mathcal{D}_s : s(x) + \gamma(\|\Delta y\|_\infty) \geq 0\}, \quad (28)$$

for some class $\mathcal{K}_{[0, \bar{d}]}$ function γ .

In analogy to the definitions of the ISSf system and ISSf set in [14], we define the output-to-state safe (OSSf) system and the OSSf set as follows:

Definition 6. Given a set $\mathcal{S}_y \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ for a continuously differentiable function $s : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and an open set \mathcal{D}_s with $\mathcal{S}_y \subset \mathcal{D}_s$, the set \mathcal{S} is an OSSf set if there exists some $\gamma \in \mathcal{K}_{[0, e]}$ satisfying $\lim_{r \rightarrow e} \gamma(r) = b$ and a constant $\bar{d} \in [0, e)$, such that for all Δy satisfying $\|\Delta y\|_\infty \leq \bar{d}$, the set $\mathcal{S}_y(\Delta y) \subset \mathcal{D}_s$ is forward invariant. The system is OSSf if it admits an OSSf set \mathcal{S}_y . ■

For system (1), and arbitrary $k_1, \dots, k_m \in \mathbb{N}$, we can redefine the output y of the system to be

$$y^{\{k_1, \dots, k_m\}} \triangleq (y_1; \dots; y_1^{(k_1)}; \dots; y_m; \dots; y_m^{(k_m)}). \quad (29)$$

By restricting the input $a(t)$ to be sufficiently smooth, the $\{k_1, \dots, k_m\}$ -output extension system of (1) is obtained as follows:

$$\dot{x} = f(x) + g(x)a(t), \quad (30a)$$

$$y^{\{k_1, \dots, k_m\}} = h(x, a, \dots, a^{(j-1)}), \quad (30b)$$

where $j = \max_{1 \leq i \leq m} k_i$. By letting y^{k_1, \dots, k_m} be the output perturbation of the system (30), we have the following definitions.

Definition 7 (Weakly Uniformly OSSf of order $\{k_1, \dots, k_m\}$). The system (1) is weakly uniformly OSSf of order $\{k_1, \dots, k_m\}$ with respect to \mathcal{S} if \mathcal{S} is an OSSf set with respect to the output $y^{\{k_1, \dots, k_m\}}$, i.e., the set $\mathcal{S}_y(\Delta y^{\{k_1, \dots, k_m\}})$ is forward invariant for any input a . ■

By defining a set κ as follows:

$$\kappa \triangleq \underbrace{\{1, \dots, 1\}}_{r_1}, \dots, \underbrace{\{k^*, \dots, k^*\}}_{r_{k^*} - r_{k^* - 1}}, \quad (31)$$

we give the following definition.

Definition 8. Suppose that Assumption 1 holds. The system (1) is strongly internally safe if it is weakly uniformly OSSf of order κ and there exists some k^* such that $r_{k^*} = m$. ■

Definition 9. Given the dynamic system (1), a continuously differentiable function $s : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a weakly uniformly output-to-state safe barrier function (OSSf-BF) for the set $\mathcal{S} \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ defined by (5) if there exists an open set \mathcal{D}_s such that $\mathcal{S} \subset \mathcal{D}_s$, functions $\alpha \in \mathcal{K}_{(-b, e)}$ and $\iota \in \mathcal{K}_{[0, e]}$ satisfying $\lim_{r \rightarrow e} \iota(r) = c$, and a constant $\bar{d} \in [0, e)$, such that

$$L_{f+ga}s(x) \geq -\alpha(s(x)) - \iota(\|y^\kappa\|_\infty) \quad (32)$$

holds for any $x \in \mathcal{D}_s$, $a \in \mathcal{A}_1$ and $y^\kappa \in \mathbb{R}^m$ satisfying $\|y^\kappa\|_\infty \leq \bar{d}$. ■

Hence, we derive the following main result.

Theorem 3. Suppose that Assumptions 1 and 2 hold. Then, any stealthy input $a(t) \in \mathcal{A}_1$ is a safe input if it admits an OSS-BF $s(x)$ such that

$$L_{f+ga}s(x) \geq -\alpha(s(x)) - \iota(\|y^\kappa\|_\infty). \quad (33)$$

holds for any $x \in \mathcal{D}_s$, $a \in \mathcal{A}_1$, and $y^\kappa \in \mathbb{R}^m$ satisfying $\|y^\kappa\|_\infty \leq \bar{d}$. ■

Based on Theorems 2 and 3, we can conclude that: (a) if the system (1) is uniformly observable, it is not vulnerable to the stealthy integrity attack; and (b) if the system (1) is not uniformly observable, but strongly internally safe, then it is also not vulnerable to the stealthy integrity attack. In the case that the system (1) is vulnerable to the stealthy integrity attack, the attack signal $a(t)$ can be parameterized by (20) and $a(t) \in \mathcal{A}_0$ (strictly stealthy attacks) or $a(t) \in \mathcal{A}_1$ (Non-strictly stealthy attacks). These results, combined with Theorem 1, which provides conditions such that no stealthy attack exists, solve Problem 1, and provide a systematic framework to assess safety against stealthy integrity attacks, offering insights into how vulnerabilities emerge in nonlinear systems and on how such vulnerabilities may be mitigated through suitable design.

V. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

This section validates the theoretical analysis of this paper through two examples, one is not vulnerable to stealthy integrity attacks, while the other is.

A. System with Safe Stealthy Input

We consider the following single input-single output system that has the form (1) and satisfies Assumptions 1 and 2: $\dot{x}_1 = x_2 - a$, $\dot{x}_2 = a$, $\dot{x}_3 = -x_3 + \frac{\sin(x_1)\sin(x_2)}{x_3^2 + 0.01}$ and $y = x_1 + x_2$. This system has a relative degree 2 and is strongly internally safe, but is not uniformly observable. The following safe set \mathcal{S} is taken into account:

$$\mathcal{S} = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^3 : s(x) \geq 0\}, \quad (34)$$

where $s(x) = 1 - \frac{x_1^2}{10} - \frac{x_2^2}{6} - \frac{x_3^2}{5}$. The projection of this safe set on the $x_1 - x_2$ plane is considered as the stealthy output set $\Delta \mathcal{Y}$ in (4), i.e.,

$$\Delta \mathcal{Y} = \left\{ \Delta x \in \mathbb{R}^2 : 1 - \frac{\Delta x_1^2}{10} - \frac{\Delta x_2^2}{6} \geq 0 \right\}. \quad (35)$$

Following the recursive steps in Section III, the attack is derived as follows:

$$a(t) = -4\Delta x_1(t) - 5\Delta x_2(t) + v(t), \quad (36)$$

where $v(t) = \sin(2\pi t)$. It can be verified by Fig. 1 that $a \in \mathcal{A}_1$, i.e., this attack is stealthy, since Δy remains in $\Delta \mathcal{Y}$.

We proceed to judge the safety of the stealthy input based on Theorem 3. Figure 2 shows the relation between $L_{f+ga}s(x)$ and $-\alpha(s(x)) - \iota(\|y^{\{1,2\}}\|_\infty)$ and verifies that the attack a is a safe input since it admits an OSS-BF $s(x)$ satisfying (36).

We conclude that the strongly internally safe system is not vulnerable to stealthy integrity attacks. This conclusion verifies Theorem 3.

Fig. 1. Stealthiness of the attack $a = -4\Delta x_1 - 5\Delta x_2 + \sin(2\pi t)$.

Fig. 2. Size relation between L_{f+ga} and $-\alpha(s(x)) - \iota(\|y^{\{1,2\}}\|_\infty)$.

B. System Vulnerable to Stealthy Attacks

The system is given as follows: $\dot{x}_1 = x_2 - a$, $\dot{x}_2 = a$, $\dot{x}_3 = -x_3 + 2.15x_3^2 \sin(x_1) \sin(x_2)$ and $y = x_1 + x_2$. Such system has a relative degree 2, but is not uniformly observable. This system is not strongly internally safe since trajectories of x_1 and x_2 that exponentially decay to zero can steer x_3 to infinity. The same safe set \mathcal{S} as in Section V-A, given by (34), and stealthy output set $\Delta\mathcal{Y}$, given by (35), are considered for the underlying system and the same attack $a(t)$, given by (36), is applied. Under this attack, the time response of the output is the same with that depicted in Fig. 1, which verifies that this attack is also a stealthy input. The distinction is that this attack is unsafe. Figure 3 demonstrates that this attack is unsafe, since the state x exceeds the safe set \mathcal{S} .

As a result, we conclude that the system lacking strong internal safety is vulnerable to the stealthy integrity attack. The latter validates our theoretical results.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper studied the vulnerability of a class of nonlinear systems against stealthy integrity attacks. A forward invariant set for the system output has been introduced to characterize the stealthiness of the attack, along a safety set to assess the safety of the attack, such that when system states remained within the safety set, the system was deemed safe. It turned out that the uniform observability of nonlinear systems is

Fig. 3. Safety of $a = -4\Delta x_1 - 5\Delta x_2 + \sin(2\pi t)$ for the safe set (34).

equivalent to their non-vulnerability against strictly stealthy integrity attacks. When the uniform observability condition is not satisfied, nonlinear systems are not vulnerable to stealthy integrity attacks if they admit an output-to-state safe barrier function. Moreover, for the nonlinear systems that are vulnerable to such attacks, we show how the stealthy integrity attacks are parameterized.

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